

RIPOSTE: A Collaborative Cyber Attack Response Framework for the Automotive Systems

Authors

I. QUESTIONNAIRE

A. Questions about the safety of the framework

- 1) What are your first and last names?
- 2) What is your highest educational degree?
 - a) B.Sc.
 - b) M.Sc.
 - c) P.hD.
 - d) Other (insert text)
- 3) What is the domain of your highest educational degree?
 - a) Computer Science and Engineering
 - b) Software Engineering
 - c) Networks and Systems
 - d) Other (insert text)
- 4) What is the name of the organization where you currently study or work in?
- 5) What is your current occupation?

Description: e.g., security expert, system architect, researcher in security, PhD student in computer science.
- 6) How many months of working experience do you have in systems security and safety?
- 7) How do you rate your expertise in systems security and safety?
 - a) 1 very low
 - b) 2 low
 - c) 3 average
 - d) 4 high
 - e) 5 very high
- 8) How do you rate the safety of the developed collaborative attack response system?
 - a) 1 extremely unsafe
 - b) 2 slightly unsafe
 - c) 3 neither unsafe or safe
 - d) 4 slightly safe
 - e) 5 very safe
- 9) How safe is it to make decisions based on automated experiments with almost no human interactions? Please elaborate.

Description: automated experiments are performed to evaluate the response techniques using the workshop cars.
- 10) How do you rate the severity of "trustworthiness" of the collaborating vehicles as a safety concern when using the developed collaborative attack response system in practice?

Description: trustworthiness: how much can the on-road car (the car that requests the evaluation) trust the results of experiments conducted on the workshop cars (the cars being experimented on).
- 11) In your opinion, how can the safety concern related to "trustworthiness" be addressed?
 - a) 1 insignificant
 - b) 2 minor
 - c) 3 moderate
 - d) 4 major
 - e) 5 severe
- 12) How do you rate the severity of "qualification" of the collaborating vehicles as a safety concern when using the developed collaborative attack response system in practice?

Description: qualification: how qualified are the workshop cars to be experimented on.
- 13) In your opinion, how can the safety concern related to "qualification" be addressed?
 - a) 1 insignificant
 - b) 2 minor
 - c) 3 moderate
 - d) 4 major
 - e) 5 severe
- 14) In your opinion, what other aspects can be considered as safety concerns when using the developed collaborative attack response system in practice?

Description: Please mention the concern, rate its severity (1 to 5), and elaborate (if possible) on how to address it.
- 15) Any other comments that you would like to mention?